

Analysis of Sandwich Panels Under Several Load Cases with Consideration of Core Compression

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
DARMSTADT

Hussam Georges^{1,2)}, Christian Mittelstedt¹⁾ and Wilfried Becker²⁾
International Conference on Composite Materials
30. July – 04. August 2023, Belfast North Irland

1) Institute for Lightweight Engineering and Structural Mechanics, Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany

2) Institute of Structural Mechanics, Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany

MASCHINENBAU **LSM**
We engineer future

Sandwich Panels Under Localized Loads

- Core failure: one of the dominated failure modes in sandwich panels
- Transverse normal stresses and core indentation induced by concentrated loads not predictable by common sandwich theories

Agenda

1. Sandwich model
2. Higher-order displacement representations
3. Load cases
4. Results
5. Conclusion and outlook

Sandwich Model

- 2D Sandwich model (plane-strain state)
- Isotropic face sheets
- Orthotropic core material:
 - Effective properties of a lattice structure
- Prediction of core stresses

Georges et al. (2023):
European Journal of
Mechanics A/Solids

Modeling Approach

- $u^{(n)} = u_0^{(n)} + z\psi^{(n)}, \quad w^{(n)} = w_0$
- $\varepsilon_{xx}^{(n)} = \frac{\partial u^{(n)}}{\partial x}, \quad \gamma_{xz}^{(n)} = \frac{\partial w^{(n)}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u^{(n)}}{\partial z}$
- $\sigma_{xx}^{(n)} = \frac{E^{(f)}}{1-\nu^{(f)}} \varepsilon_{xx}^{(n)} \quad \tau_{xz}^{(n)} = G^{(f)} \gamma_{xz}^{(n)}$
- $\Pi_i^{(n)} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} \int_{-h^{(f)}/2}^{h^{(f)}/2} (\sigma_{xx}^{(n)} \varepsilon_{xx}^{(n)} + \tau_{xz}^{(n)} \gamma_{xz}^{(n)}) dz dx$

Higher-Order Displacement Representations

$$\bullet \quad u^{(c)} = \frac{u_0^{(1)} + u_0^{(2)} + \frac{h^{(f)}}{2}\psi^{(1)} - \frac{h^{(f)}}{2}\psi^{(2)}}{2} + \frac{-u_0^{(1)} + u_0^{(2)} - \frac{h^{(f)}}{2}\psi^{(1)} - \frac{h^{(f)}}{2}\psi^{(2)}}{h^{(c)}} z + \tilde{u}\tilde{F} + \hat{u}\hat{H} + \check{u}\check{R}$$

$$\bullet \quad w^{(c)} = \frac{w_0^{(1)} + w_0^{(2)}}{2} + \frac{w_0^{(2)} - w_0^{(1)}}{h^{(c)}} z + \tilde{w}\tilde{F} + \hat{w}\hat{H} + \check{w}\check{R}$$

$$\bullet \quad \varepsilon_{xx}^{(c)} = \frac{\partial u^{(c)}}{\partial x}, \quad \varepsilon_{zz}^{(c)} = \frac{\partial w^{(c)}}{\partial z}, \quad \gamma_{xz}^{(c)} = \frac{\partial w^{(c)}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u^{(c)}}{\partial z}$$

$$\bullet \quad \tilde{F}(z) = \left(1 - \frac{4z^2}{h^{(c)2}}\right)$$

$$\bullet \quad \hat{H}(z) = \tilde{F}(z) z$$

$$\bullet \quad \check{R}(z) = \tilde{F}(z) z^2$$

Core's Potential Energy

- $\Pi_i^{(c)} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} \int_{-h^{(c)}/2}^{h^{(c)}/2} (\sigma_{xx}^{(c)} \varepsilon_{xx}^{(c)} + \sigma_{zz}^{(c)} \varepsilon_{zz}^{(c)} + \tau_{xz}^{(c)} \gamma_{xz}^{(c)}) dz dx$

- $\Pi = \Pi_i^{(1)} + \Pi_i^{(2)} + \Pi_i^{(c)} + \Pi_e$

- $\delta\Pi = 0 \rightarrow 12$ coupled second-order differential equations

- $\underline{\dot{\Phi}} = \underline{\underline{E}} \underline{\Phi}$, with $\underline{\Phi} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\Psi} \\ \underline{\dot{\Psi}} \end{bmatrix}$, and $\underline{\Psi} = [u_0^{(1)} \quad u_0^{(2)} \quad \dots]^T$

- General solution: $\underline{\Phi}_h = \sum_{m=1}^{24} K_m \underline{v}_m e^{\lambda_m x}$

Load cases

FE Model

- 2D analysis using Abaqus
- Plane strain quadratic solid elements
- $E^{(f)}=70000 \text{ MPa}$, $\nu^{(f)}=0.35$
- Thin face sheets: $\frac{h^{(c)}}{h^{(f)}} = 15$
- Thick sandwich: $\frac{\bar{l}}{h^{(c)}} = 4$

3-Point Bending

4-Point Bending

Fixed-End Sandwich Beam

Horizontal displacement u in mm

Vertical displacement w in mm

Normalized stress $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$ or $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}$ in $\frac{1}{\text{mm}^2}$

Cantilever Sandwich Beam

Restrained Sandwich Beam

Introducing Mathematical Sublayers

- $u^{(c,j)} = \chi^{(c,2)} + 2 \frac{\chi^{(c,j+1)} - \chi^{(c,j)}}{h^{(c)}} z + \tilde{u}^{(c,j)} \tilde{F}^{(c,j)} + \hat{u}^{(c,j)} \hat{H}^{(c,j)}$

- $w^{(c,j)} = \zeta^{(c,2)} + 2 \frac{\zeta^{(c,j+1)} - \zeta^{(c,j)}}{h^{(c)}} z + \tilde{w}^{(c,j)} \tilde{F}^{(c,j)} + \hat{w}^{(c,j)} \hat{H}^{(c,j)}$

- $\tilde{F}^{(c,j)}(z) = \frac{8(3-2j)}{h^{(c)}} z - \left(\frac{4}{h^{(c)}} z \right)^2$

- $\hat{H}^{(c,j)}(z) = \tilde{F}^{(c,j)}(z) z$

Localized Deformation on Edges

Horizontal displacement u in mm
12 DOF (single layer)

Horizontal displacement u in mm
15 DOF (2 math. layers)

Horizontal displacement u in mm
25 DOF (4 math. layers)

Conclusion

- Efficient determination of core compression in several load cases
- Sufficient prediction of critical core stresses induced by concentrated loads
- Capturing of localized free-edge deformation by introducing mathematical layers
- Outlook:
 - Grading the core material and optimizing the core weight

Hussam Georges, M.Sc.

 [+49 6151-16 22024](tel:+4961511622024)

 hussam.georges@klub.tu-darmstadt.de

Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany

Institute for Lightweight Engineering and

Structural Mechanics

 www.klub.tu-darmstadt.de

